
Financial Independency of the Working Wives (An Empirical Study in the Fields of Law and Shariah)

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Abstract

This empirical study aimed to shed a light on financial independency of the working wives from the perspectives of the ones specialized in law and shariah. The provisions regulating financial independency aim to regulate the financial issues related to spouses due to having common funds. They aim to regulate the financial issues, because the marital relationship hinders wives from claiming for their financial rights in most cases. The present study aimed to shed a light on the provisions in Shariah and the provision of the Jordanian Personal Status Law and other laws in this regard.

The researchers of the study adopted an inductive descriptive approach. It was found that the existence of the marital relationship is neither a reason for the elimination of financial independency of the working wives nor a reason for merging it with financial independency of the husband. In fact, under the provisions of the law and shariah, the working wives have an independent financial independency which grants them the right to dispose her funds. However, having legislations granting the working wives this right is not enough to protect her financial rights. Therefore, the present study aimed to offer several suggestions after reviewing the relevant laws. For instance, the researchers of the present study recommends drafting a bill that aims at letting the family and women experience psychological stability. After approving the bill, the law must be added to the Jordanian Personal Status Law.

Keywords

Financial Independency, Financial Independency of Spouses, Financial Relationship between the Spouses, Division of Funds between the Spouses.

Introduction:

Allah created people from one spirit. He created its mate from it. In this regard, a verse in the Holy Quran states the following: (O mankind! Be careful of your duty to your Lord Who created you from a single soul and from it created its mate and from them twain hath spread abroad a multitude of men and women. Be careful of your duty toward Allah in Whom ye claim (your rights) of one another, and toward the wombs (that bore you). Lo! Allah hath been a Watcher over you. (Al-Nisa' Surah, Verse No. 1). Allah made finding rest based on love and compassion. In this regard, a verse in the Holy Quran states the

following: (And one of His signs is that He created mates for you from yourselves that you may find rest in them, and He put between you love and compassion; most surely there are signs in this for a people who reflect (Al-Room Surah, Verse No. 21). In order for the family members to enjoy a state of psychological stability, Shariah includes provisions for identifying the rights and duties of spouses towards each other. In this regard, a verse in the Holy Quran states the following: (And they (women) have rights similar to those (of men) over them in kindness) (Al-Baqarah Surah, Verse No. 228). Amongst the rights granted to humans are the right to possess and the right to dispose funds in a manner that's halal. That applies provided that one enjoys full capacity. There is not any difference between man and woman in this regard. The marital relationship involves having cooperation between the spouses. It involves sharing the financial and moral responsibilities. Due to the nature of the marital relationship, wives usually fulfill the financial duties willingly or under coercion in order to assist their husbands. Such financial duties include: the financial duties needed for buying a house. Today, fulfilling financial duties became harder for the family members. Due to having financial duties that are difficult to fulfill, women have been playing a significant role in assisting men in fulfilling such duties. In fact, women have not been only assisting men through spending money. In fact, they have been taking debts and bank loans with deducting installments from their monthly salaries to assist men financially. They have been doing that without having an official document proving that they have been doing that. That is because the marital relationship serves as a moral barrier hindering women from claiming for such proofs. In fact, claiming for such proofs shall lead to having doubts between spouses. Such doubts shall lead to having disputes between them. They shall lead to eliminating love and compassion and hindering them from finding rest at home. Thus, they shall hinder spouses from meeting the goals sought from marriage in Shariah.

Wives sometimes believe that refraining from claiming for such proofs is something accepted when having a stable marital relationship. However, such refraining shall lead to depriving women from their rights when having divorce or when the husband marries to another woman. It shall lead to having problems in such cases, especially in case the properties are registered under the name of the husband only. That makes the financial issues a real threat to the stability of families. Thus, how can the legislator regulate the financial issues between spouses? What are the barriers that hinder such regulation? Are such barriers shariah-based barriers, or legal or social based barriers? Answers for these are presented below:

Statement of the Problem:

This study aimed to answer the questions below:

Q.1. What are the provisions in Shariah that regulate financial independency of the working wives?

Q.2. What are the legislations that address financial independency of the working wives? What is the stand of the legislators of other laws on financial independency of the working wives?

Q.3. What is the reality of financial independency of the working wives in the Jordanian society?

The Significance of the Study:

The significance of the study is shown below:

- 1) The present study presents the provisions in Shariah that regulate financial independency of the working wife. It also presents the provisions in the Jordanian laws that regulate financial independency of the working wife. It presents such provisions with shedding a light on all aspects.
- 2) The present study enriches the relevant Arab literature in the fields of Shariah and law. It enriches it through offering theoretical and empirical knowledge that relates to reality in the Jordanian society.
- 3) The present study offers a comparison between financial independency of wives and financial independency of husbands. The researcher of the present study recommends drafting a bill that aims to achieve justice in this regard and resolve the disputes about financial issues between spouses.

The objectives of the study:

The present study aimed to:

- 1) Identify the provisions in Shariah that regulate financial independency of the working wives
- 2) Identify the provisions regulating financial independency of the working wives in the Jordanian law. It aimed to identify the stand of the legislators of other laws on financial independency of the working wives.
- 3) Explore the reality of financial independency of the working wives in the Jordanian society.

Previous Studies:

First: Studies in the field of Shariah

First: Al-Kilani, Jamal. The right of wives to dispose their salaries and the impact of that on the stability of the marital relationship. *Dirasat Journal*. 2007.

The latter researcher aimed to explore ruling (i.e. the stand of shariah) on women's right to dispose their own funds and the impact of that on family. He found that women are independent financially. In addition to that no one is entitled to anything from her funds unless she approves that willingly. That applies whether this person is a spouse, father, or brother. The latter researcher found that dealing in an authoritative manner with women without having the right to is considered ill-gotten and a form of oppression under shariah. However, he found that the working wife has financial responsibilities, such as:

paying off the household expenditures in case the husband required that as a condition before marriage in an explicit or implicit manner. The financial responsibilities of the working wife involves assisting in supporting her children financially in case the husband is experiencing financial hardship. They include assisting her brothers in supporting her poor parents financially.

Second: Al-En'airat, Ayman. financial independency of women under Islamic Jurisprudence (Fqih). An-Najah National University. 2009.

The latter researcher aimed to identify the provision in Shariah that are related to the financial rights of women. He aimed to identify the provision in Shariah that are related to woman's job and contributions in paying off the household expenditures. Also, He aimed to identify the provision in Shariah that are related to woman's role in supporting husband, ascendants, and descendants financially. He found that women have an independent financial through which they have rights similar to men without conditions or constraints. Women have the required capacity that allows them to work and earn money in accordance with certain conditions and regulations. The funds that women earn are considered their own possessions. Women may have financial responsibilities to fulfil towards their husbands. Husbands are allowed to prevent women from working in certain cases. The funds that women get from working are considered assets that fall under their own possessions in their financial independence.

The aforementioned studies shed a light on the financial responsibilities of the working wives towards their family. As for the present study, it sheds a light on the financial rights and responsibilities of the working wives under shariah and law.

Second: Studies in the field of law:

Rahmah, Kinzi, and Haybah, Lam'oosh. The financial acquisitions acquired after marriage: A study in the fields of law and fqih. Algeria. University of Bejaia. 2015.

The latter researchers aimed to explore the way in which the funds are divided between the spouses. They aimed to shed a light on the nature of the funds acquired by spouses. They aimed to explore the way of dividing the funds between spouses in case there is a dispute between them on the funds or the marital relationship ended due to divorce or death.

The latter researchers aimed to explore the shortcomings of the Algerian laws related to the common funds between the spouses. They found that the Algerian laws do not identify the meaning of the term (common funds). They found that the Algerian laws do not identify the means –other than writing- that can be used to prove one's possession for the financial acquisitions in case there is a dispute. The Algerian laws shed a light on the common possession for the acquisitions in the house. Hence, provisions must be acted by the Algerian legislator to protect the spouses' possession for the latter acquisitions. Provisions must be acted by the Algerian legislator to protect the family and regulate the wives' contribution in paying off the household expenditures.

The present study differs from this one by recommends drafting a bill that regulate the issues related to the common funds of spouses. The present study includes an empirical aspect that shed a light on the reality of financial independency of the working wives in the Jordanian society. For instance, it includes a questionnaire which was used to obtain data from a sample selected from the members of the Jordanian society.

Third: Studies in the field of Education:

First: Al-Sarayrah, Burshrah. The impact of empowerment on granting the working women a financial independency and the impact of that on family violence in the Jordanian families from the perspective of spouses: Karak as a model. Karak. Mu'tah University. 2016.

The latter researcher aimed to explore the relationship between- financial disclosure of the working women and its impact on family violence in the Jordanian families in Karak. The researcher aimed to explore that in accordance with several variables (i.e., gender, common monthly income, place of residence, academic qualification and etc...). The sample consists of 465 working women who were chosen randomly from Karak, Jordan. The latter researcher reached several results. For instance, she found that the respondents realize the significance of empowering the working women in economic areas in order for them to have an independent financial closure. She found that having an independent financial closure by working women have positive impacts on family from the perspective of respondents.

Second: Khudur and Al-Najar (2015). The contribution of working women in paying off the household expenditures and its impact on the decision-making power within the family.

The latter study aimed to explore the impact of the contribution of working women in paying off the household expenditures on the decision-making power within the family. The targets decisions are the decisions related to consumption, raising up children and family social relationships. The researchers aimed to explore whether there are differences between respondents' attitudes which can be attributed to certain social or economic variables. The research was on a sample consists of 380 working women who were chosen randomly from the public and private sectors in Giza, Cairo, Egypt. The researchers reached several results. For instance, they found that there is statistically significant difference between the respondents' degree of enjoying the family decision which can be attributed to demographic and descriptive variables. They found that there is a correlative relationship between the contribution of working women in paying off the household expenditures and the decision-making power within the family.

Contrary to the latter two studies, the present study sheds a light on legal and shariah-based aspects related to financial closure of working wives. Contrary to the latter two studies, the items of the questionnaire in the present study sheds a light on the reality of financial independency of the working wives in the Jordanian society. Those wives were chosen from the University of Jordan society.

The Study Approach:

The researchers of the present study adopted the following approaches:

The inductive approach: The researchers adopted this approach to analyze the opinions of the ones specialized in Fqih to reach a ruling.

The comparative approach: The researchers adopted this approach to carry out a comparison between the provisions of civil laws, provisions of shariah, and provisions of other laws.

The critical approach: The researchers adopted this approach to set a vision for the bill which regulate financial independency of working wives.

The descriptive approach: The researchers adopted this approach to explore the reality of financial independency of the working wives in the Jordanian society from a legal and shariah-based perspectives. The latter approach fits with the gaols and topic of the present study.

Study Structure:

This study is divided into three parts and structured as follows:

Background information: The meaning of financial independency of the working wives.

First part: financial independency of the working wives and the associated rights and duties, divided into two sections as follows:

First section: The right of the working wife to own and dispose her funds.

Second section: The financial rights and duties related to women's wage.

Second part: The stand of the legislator of the Jordanian laws on financial independency of the working wives in comparison with the legislators of other laws and the benefits gained from such laws, which is also divided into two sections as follows:

First section: The opinion of the legislator of the Jordanian laws about financial independency of the working wives.

Second section: The opinion of the legislators of other laws about financial independency of the working wives and the benefits gained from such laws.

Third part: The reality of financial independency of the working wives in the Jordanian society.

At the end, **Conclusion, and recommendations** of the study are presented.

Background Information:**The Meaning of Financial Independency of the Working Wives:**

Financial independency is a compound term of two parts, (independency) and (money). The following is a clarification of their meaning in the dictionary meaning and technical:

The Dictionary and Idiomatic meaning of Financial Independency:**The Dictionary meaning of Financial Independency:**

Financial independency is a term that refers to pact, guarantee, security, or right. It involves the things that one pledges to fulfil and do (Al-Rafe'y, 2008). In simple words, it refers to the things that one commits himself/herself to fulfil.

The Idiomatic meaning of Financial Independency:

Financial independency is a term used by Allah in the Holy Quran for describing humans. It was used in the following verse: (And (remember) when thy Lord brought forth from the Children of Adam, from their reins, their seed, and made them testify of themselves, (saying): Am I not your Lord? They said: Yea, verily. We testify. (That was) lest ye should say at the Day of Resurrection: Lo! of this we were unaware) (Al-A'raf Surah, Verse No. 172). In the latter verse, Allah tells people about the pact between him and the children of Adam. Under this pact, the children of Adam shall be held liable for negligence in doing their duties that Allah sets. The use of the term Thema means that one enjoys the required legal and shariah-based capacity.

Regarding the idiomatic meaning of financial independency, it is a term used for suggesting that one has the required capacity that qualifies him/her to make an offer and accept it (Al-Bukhari, 2009). It is used for suggesting that one has the required capacity that qualifies him/her to have rights and duties (Al-Sanhoori, 2017). The latter definition is criticized because it suggests that the financial independency involves only the capacity to make an offer (Al-Qudah, 2010). In response to such a criticism, it is suggested that the capacity to make an offer requires having a valid financial independency (Al-Bukhari, 2009). Under shariah, there are several conditions for enjoying a valid financial independency. For instance, maturity and having a sound mind are required conditions to have a valid financial disclosure (Al-Qarafi, 2009). financial independency is also defined as a shariah-based term indicating that one can be held responsible and can hold others responsible (Al-Qarafi, 2009). It means that one has the required capacity that allows him/her to have rights and duties. The latter definition is criticized because this definition considers the financial independency as term indicating only that one has the capacity to act (Al-Qudah, 2010). financial independency is also defined as a legal person who enjoys rights (Al-Zarqa', 1999). The latter definition indicates that financial independency is something virtual that does not actually exist. It suggests that it can be enjoyed by legal persons and allow them to have rights.

In term of money, the dictionary meaning of financial independency is derived from the term (funds). The term funds refer to the monetary assets (Al-FayroozAbabdi, 2005).

The meaning of the term (funds) is debatable. Some scholars in fqih suggest that funds refer to everything that is considered valuable by people and can be used to benefit from in a manner that's halal (Al-Jazeezi, 2004). According to the ones who adopt the Hanafi School, funds refer to everything that can be possessed and used to benefit from (Ibn Abdeen, 2003).

Financial Independency as a Compound term:

Under fqih, financial Independency is an adjective indicating that one has financial rights and duties. Such rights include financial rights of Allah and financial rights of people which must be fulfilled by one. financial Independency of a working wife is defined as an aspect of a legal personality that is enjoyed by working wife, grants her financial rights and assigns her financial duties.

Part 1: Financial independency of the working wives and it is associated rights and duties:

This part consists of two sections as below:

First section: The right of the working wife to own and dispose her funds:

It must be agreed that women and men are both created by Allah. Islam addressed issues related for both of them without showing any discrimination. It is free from any discrimination that is based on gender, colour, or race. In this regard, a verse in the Holy Quran states the following: (O mankind! Be careful of your duty to your Lord Who created you from a single soul and from it created its mate and from them twain hath spread abroad a multitude of men and women. Be careful of your duty toward Allah in Whom ye claim (your rights) of one another, and toward the wombs (that bore you). Lo! Allah hath been a Watcher over you). (Al-Nisa' Surah, Verse No. 1). Based on this verse, Allah created all people from a single soul. He created a mate for each soul. In fact, Eve was created from Adam. Such information is consistent with the following Hadith: (Prophet Mohammad said: (Women are the twin halves of men) (Al-Tarmathi, 2014). This hadith means that women are created from men (Ibn Manthoor, 1988). Under Shariah, men and women are considered equal in terms of rights and duties. In this regard, a verse in the Holy Quran states the following: (And they (women) have rights similar to those (of men) over them in kindness.) (Al-Baqarah Surah, Verse No. 228). The household responsibilities are shared between husband and wife. However, responsibilities are allocated to husband and wife based on the qualification and capacity of each one. The role of husbands complements the role of wives in order to achieve justice. For instance, the responsibilities of wives include getting pregnant, breastfeeding, and staying up late and exerting effort to take care of their children. In order for wives to have adequate time to fulfil such responsibilities, wives must be provided with protection and care and their needs must be met by their husbands. Hence, wives are not obliged to work to get money. In fact, women -throughout all their lives- must be financially supported by the men responsible for them. The men responsible for such support may be husbands or fathers. Despite that, Islam grants women and men the right to own and the right to dispose funds. That is because both men and women have the legal capacity to own and dispose funds. There are several texts in Hadith and Holy Quran that suggest that women have the right to own. In this regard, a verse in the Holy Quran states the following: (men shall have the benefit of what they earn, and women shall have the benefit of what they earn) (Al-Nisa' Surah, Verse No. 32). In terms of women's right to dispose, a verse in the Holy Quran states the following: (For you half of what your wives leave if they have no child. If they have a child, a quarter of what they leave shall be yours after any bequest she had be-

queathed, or any debt) (Al-Nisa' Surah, Verse No. 12). There is another verse that addresses women's right to dispose which is the following: (And unto them belong the fourth of that which ye leave if ye have no child, but if ye have a child then the eighth of that which ye leave, after any legacy ye may have bequeathed, or debt (Al-Nisa' Surah, Verse No. 11). Thus, based on the textual sources of Shariah, the inherited money can be disposed to the heirs only after checking whether there the deceased had financial responsibilities that he/she didn't fulfil, or the deceased written will. That applies whether the deceased is a man or woman. In addition, based on the textual sources of Shariah, women can exercise their right to dispose their funds without getting the approval or their husbands or the men responsible for them. That is stipulated through the following Hadith: Prophet Mohammad said: (Oh' Women, you must give charity even if it is from your own jewels) (Al-Bukhari, 2015). Based on the latter hadith, wives aren't obliged to take the approval of their husbands before exercising the right of disposal (i.e., giving charity). That is because if taking such an approval is obligatory, Prophet Mohammad would have mentioned it (Ibn Qudamah, 2010).

Maymoonah bint Al-Hareth freed a female slave named Walida without taking the permission of Prophet Mohammad. When Maymoonah bint Al-Hareth saw the prophet, she told him about what she did. The prophet told her that giving Walida to her maternal uncles would have been considered a better deed. However, the prophet did not blame her (Al-Bukhari, 2015). That means that women can exercise the right to dispose without asking men for permission.

According to Al-Shafi' (1990), the female or male person who becomes mature has the right to dispose his /her own funds. The same applies to man and woman, whether the woman is married or not. Marriage does not restrict woman's right to dispose her funds (Al-Shafi, 1990). In other words, women have the right to own and dispose her funds in any manner that is deemed halal. For instance, they can purchase, sell, rent, and mortgage things. They can conclude financial contract by themselves without having an intermediate. They can assign an agent to act on their behalf in financial issues. They can file lawsuits before the court against others to protect their financial rights. The adult woman can exercise her right to dispose her funds whether her husband is present or absent. Such exercise involves selling and renting properties (Ibn Hazem, 1998).

As for woman's right to dispose all her funds in charity or part of it, it is halal from the perspective of the ones adopting Hanafi School (Al-Kasani, 2003), Al-Shafi' School (Al-Nawawi, 1991), and Al-Hanbali School (Ibn Qudama Al-Maqdasi, 1995). That is stipulated in verses in the Holy Quran and tests in Sunnah. Such texts are identified in the aforementioned paragraphs in the present study.

As for the ones adopting Al-Malaki School (Al-Hattab, 1992) and the ones adopting Al-Hanableh School (Ibn Mefleh, 1983), they suggest that taking the husbands' approval is required for woman to exercise her right to dispose her funds. According to the ones adopting Al-Malaki School, taking such approval is required in case woman wants to exercise this right in an amount that exceeds one third of her funds. The ones adopting Al-

Malaki School required that in the aim of protecting women's financial rights. They base their view in this regard on the following Hadith: (Prophet Mohammad states the following: (Woman is not allowed to dispose her funds if Issma (infallibility) is enjoyed by her husband)) (Abu Dawood, 2009). In other words, they restrict woman's right to dispose to the amount that is less than one third of her funds (Muslim, 2006). Ibn Majah states that the latter Hadith is not well-proved. He adds that Quran proved that this Hadith is not valid (Ibn Majah, 2009). Based on most of the schools of Fqih, taking the husband's approval in this regard is desirable to show respect and avoid conflicts (Al-Shokani, 1993). Based on most of the schools of Fqih, it is desirable to ensure the stability of the family. It is a goal sought by Shariah.

A decision issued by the International Islamic Fqih Academy states the following: (Wives enjoy full capacity and have an independent financial independence. They have the full right to dispose their wage and own wealth in accordance with the provisions of Shariah. They enjoy the right to own assets and dispose their possessions. Husbands do not have authority to act in their wives' funds. Wives do not need the approval of their husbands to own assets nor acts in her funds) (The International Islamic Fqih Academy, 2005)

Second section: The financial right and duties related to women's wage:

Women have the right to own and dispose their own funds. Despite that, the working woman financially must be supported by the man responsible for her. That is stipulated in the Holy Quran, Sunnah, and views of all specialists in Fqih. In this regard, a verse in the Holy Quran states the following: (Let the rich spend according to his wealth) (Al-Talaq Surah, Verse No. 7). Prophet Mohammad said: ("They (women) have rights over you (the men) to provide them with their sustenance and clothing in a reasonable manner." [Muslim reported it]. Under the provisions of Shariah, husbands must support their wives financially under the marriage contract. That is because wives devote themselves to fulfil their household responsibilities and responsibilities towards their husbands and children (Al-En'airat, 2009). The provisions of Shariah oblige husbands to support their wives financially in the aim of promoting social solidarity in society. They oblige husbands to support their wives financially to meet the needs of the family members which must be met by wives and husbands (Abu Al-Basel, 2002). The specialists in Fqih suggest that husbands are obliged to support wives financially under a shariah based rule called (prisoner's right). This rule suggests that every person who is prisoned for meeting someone's benefit must be financially supported by the beneficiary (Ibn Abdeen, 1992).

Some specialists (e.g., Al-Ghyaini Al-Benaya) in Fqih suggest that wives must be financially supported since the time of consummation of marriage. Other specialists (e.g., Al-Nawawi Rawdah) in Fqih suggest that wives must be financially supported since the time of concluding the marriage contract. In case the husband permits his wife to work in accordance with the provisions of Shariah, it means that the husband accepts to waive all or his rights in some aspects, because his wife is busy working (Al-Hattab, 1992). Under Shariah, in case a man married a working woman, the man isn't entitled to prevent his

wife from working. Under Shariah, in case a man married a working woman, the woman shall not be considered disobedient to her husband if she went to work against his will (Al-Sartawi, 2010). That is because the man's acknowledgment for the woman's employment status before marriage means that he accepted that at the time of concluding the marriage contract. Al-Sawi suggests: (It is halal for any man to get married to a woman with acknowledging something about her. That means that the man accepts waiving his rights in certain aspect) (Al-Sawi, 2013). The men who marry working women are not entitled to prevent her from working. That is because such prevention shall cause damages to her which is haram in Shariah.

In case women started working without getting their husbands' permission, the women shall not be entitled to claim for financial support because they are considered disobedient (Al-Sherbeeni, 2004). That applies unless their jobs are considered Fard Kefayah¹. Such jobs include: the professions of female doctors and washer of dead bodies. In other words, if the women decided to start working in jobs that are considered Fard Kefayah, women can start working without getting their husbands' permission (Al-Kamal Ibn Al-Hamam, 2003). Under shariah, husbands cannot inform their wives that they can permit them to work, provided that they get a certain amount of their wages. Doing that is considered haram, because this condition is an infringement for the marriage contract. The same is suggested by most of the scholars specialized in contemporary Fqih. In simple words, setting this condition is haram. The financial support provided by the working women is not considered Wajib² in all cases.

There are many proofs in the sources of Shariah supporting the validity of the latter information. Such proofs include: the following verse in the Holy Quran: (Give women their dowries freely, but if they are pleased to offer you any of it, consume it good and smooth.) (A-Nisa' Surah, Verse No. 4). In case it is haram for the man to take funds from his wife in a certain case, the man must refrain from taking funds from her in compliance with the provisions of Shariah (Al-Shafe'y, 1994).

Having a wife working shall often lead to increasing the costs and expenditures. That shall increase the financial and psychological burdens enforced on husband. Such burdens include having an increase in the extent of buying clothes by the wife. They include having to eat at restaurants sometimes. They include having to recruit a maid and having to put children at nurseries (Al-Kilani, 2007). To achieve justice, the International Islamic Fqih Academy (2005) suggests that the working wife must pay off the costs incurred due to having her working. It states the following: (The working wife must not contribute to paying off the expenditures that must be paid off by the husband in first place. It is haram to oblige the wife to do that. However, in case there are costs incurred due to having the

¹Fard Kefayah: is a term in Shariah. It refers to a legal obligation that must be fulfilled by Muslims because there aren't enough people in society to fulfil such an obligation.

²Wajib: is a term in Shairha. It refers to an obligation that must be fulfilled under the provision of shariah.

wife working, the wife must pay off such costs) (The International Islamic Fqih Academy, 2005).

There are working wives who use their wage to contribute to paying off the price of a real estate. Under shariah, in the latter case, the wife must own part of the real estate based on the amount of funds she has paid. There are working wives who use their wage to contribute to paying off the cost of a business project. Under shariah, in the latter case, the wife must get a percentage of the profits of the business project. This percentage is determined based on the amount of funds she has paid (The International Islamic Fqih Academy, 2005). That applies provided that it's proved that the wife used her wage to contribute to paying off the price of a real estate or the cost of a project. That can be provided through written proofs or other types of proofs (Rahmah and Wahibah, 2015).

Part 2: Jordanian law opinion inregarding to financial independency of the working wives compared to other laws and the extent of benefiting gained from such laws:

This part includes two sections divided as follows:

First section: Jordanian law opinion inregarding to financial independency of the working wives:

Laws are considered legislations that identify the rights and obligations of people. A law can be defined as a legislation involving a set of rules which were set to comply with them in social or public institutions to regulate people's behaviours (Robertson, 2006). Those rules are applicable to all people in the state. In this regard, article 6, paragraph 1 of the Jordanian constitution states the following: (Jordanians shall be equal before the law. There shall be no discrimination between them regarding their rights and duties on grounds of race, language or religion) (The Council of Ministers, 2011).

The issues related to Financial Disclosure of the working wives are regulated through the civil law. The civil law is a private law that aims at regulating the relationship between people who do not have a work relationship with each other (Al-Jboori, 2011). It regulates two types of relationships between people. The relationships related to financial transactions, and relationships related to personal status. The following points must be identified:

First: There is not any text in the Jordanian law that constraints woman's capacity to make contracts, It should be noted that capacity must be enjoyed by one to hold one liable for his acts and sayings. Otherwise, one's sayings and acts do not have any effect (Al-Qudah, 2012). Article 203, of the Jordanian Personal Status Law states the following:

- a. Every person who reached the age of maturity, enjoys a sound mind and his assets aren't seized earlier has the full capacity to exercise his/her civil rights.
- b. The age of maturity is represented in reaching 18 solar years.

Under the latter article, reaching the age of maturity is a condition for enjoying the full rights. That applies if one's assets are not seized. There is not any difference between males and females in this regard. Under the latter article, there is not any difference between disposing funds in a business transaction or in charity. One's right to exercise

his/her civil rights does not require the permission of anyone, provided that one enjoys the full capacity to do that.

Second: The marital relationship is not a reason for eliminating financial independency of the working wives or merging it with husbands.

Having relationships between people (e.g., marriage) is not a reason for merging financial disclosure of someone with financial disclosure of another person. That applies regardless of the rights and duties arising from the relationship. In this regard, article 320 of the Jordanian Personal Status Law states the following: (Every spouse is financially independent from the other) (The Supreme Judge Department, 2019). Every spouse has his/her own properties which he/she can dispose at any time and in any manner he/she wants. Having an independent financial independence by every spouse means that every spouse can dispose his/her funds without getting permission from the other. In simple words, the funds and debits of the husband belongs to him only and the funds and debits of the wife belongs to her only. No one is obliged to disclose information to his/her spouse about his/her financial independence. No one is entitled to get any of his/her own funds from anyone without getting permission. The financial independence of each spouse applies to the possessions that were acquired before marriage and the possessions that were acquired after marriage. That means that the financial independence applies to funds acquired by woman before marriage (i.e., heritage, dowry, and gift). However, husbands are obliged to support their wives and children financially.

Second section: The opinion of the legislators of other laws about Financial Disclosure of the working wives and the benefits gained from such laws.

The stipulation of the financial independence of the spouses is not sufficient to protect the financial rights of the spouses, specifically the working wife, which negatively affects family stability. Because the nature of the marital relationship requires the need for continuous cooperation between the spouses, especially in light of the economic situation that is increasing its burden on family's day after day, and the wife's spending in such cases is often without having any official or customary document proving her material right, so her right is threatened with loss and here, the law must intervene to solve this problem. This problem threatens many families and societies, and the following is a statement of some comparative legislation and the extent of its benefit:

The French legislator is the first legislator who regulates joint ownership between the spouses. He suggests that the spouses' funds are subject to the subscription system unless the spouses state that their marriage is subject to another financial system through a special agreement concluded between them and is associated with the marriage contract concluded before the notary or when the financial system is modified during marital life. However, the two parties must choose the system of legal participation, agreement participation, or financial independence stipulated in article (1536), and according to this agreement, each spouse is alone in managing his own property and disposes of it freely,

and each husband remains committed to his personal debts, whether that was before marriage or after it.

Under article 1497, the money acquired shall be shared between the spouses from the date of the conclusion of the marriage contract. It shall be divided upon the dissolution of this contract. It is also possible at any stage of the marriage to agree on several conditions or conditions to confirm or clarify the status of legal participation or to change any part in it. The following article also defines the issue of the spouses' earnings that come from personal economic activity or savings on entrances and private property. Several Arab countries have benefited recently from this law, including Algeria. Article (37) of the Algerian family law states the following: (the spouses may, in the marriage contract or a subsequent formal contract, agree on the common funds between them), while in Tunisia this system was called the property sharing system, and Article (94) came to stipulate the following four chapters:

Chapter one: The property-sharing system is an optional system that spouses may choose upon concluding the marriage contract or later, and it aims to make real estate or a group of real estate joint property between the spouses whenever it is one of the family's belongings.

Chapter Two: If the spouses state that they choose the property sharing system, they are subject to the provisions of this law. However, they are entitled to agree to expand the scope of participation, provided that it is explicitly stated in the contract.

Chapter Three: Choosing the property sharing system cannot prejudice the inheritance rules.

Chapter Four: The dowry is not included in the communal property and remains private to the wife. (Ministry of Justice, 2007)

Meanwhile, in Morocco, article (49) includes the following statement: (Each of the spouses has a Financial Disclosure that is independent of the responsibility of the other. However, it's permissible for spouses in the framework of the provision of funds that will be acquired during the matrimonial investment and distribution). (Ministry of Justice, 2016)

This is what some laws dealt with. To benefit from them in solving financial marital problems, the following information must be clarified:

First: The system of sharing property between spouses is an optional system in which the spouses choose between two systems of ownership: either the individual ownership system, meaning for all of his independent financial responsibility, or the ownership partnership system, which makes the money acquired after marriage joint property between the spouses unless its ownership is transferred to one of them in the face of inheritance or the gift or will. However, the French legislator intervenes and obligates the spouses in the event that a financial system is not chosen for them, or if the spouses do not declare that they are subject to a specific financial contribution system.

Second: The goal of financial participation is represented in reaching a financial agreement that preserves the right of the spouses by making the money acquired after marriage

a joint property between them, whenever they agree on that. This agreement aims to preserve the stability of the family in light of the changing living conditions that have imposed on the spouses a new way of life.

Third: The financial subscription contract. It is considered one of the specific contracts in which each contractor determines his/her rights and obligations upon concluding the contract. It is considered a time contract. That is because it allows the spouses to determine the date of the financial contribution to divide the property and the date of its beginning and end, it may start from the date of the marriage contract or a later date. It is also possible to determine the period of participation. That is subject to the desire of the spouses. Thus, spouses are completely free to determine the time (Al-Azzawi, 2010)

Fourth: Subscription Properties: All the funds acquired during the marital life is considered jointly owned by the spouses under French law, and Algerian and Moroccan law excludes money acquired through inheritance unless there is an agreement stating otherwise. Under the Tunisian law, the property shared is limited to real estate, but it grants the spouses the right to Expanding the system by virtue of a contract subsequent to the marriage contract to include all property belonging to them by ownership regardless of its source (gift, inheritance, will) and whatever the date it was acquired before or after marriage, with the exception of the dowry that remains private to the wife.

There may be no problem in the law regarding the individual property system, that is, for all its independent financial responsibility, this is the origin, but the legal wording in some articles of the French law is based on the premise that the duty of family spending is the responsibility of both spouses. That is not consistent with the provisions of Shariah. The provisions of Shariah assigns the responsibility of spending on the family is the responsibility to the husband only (RahmaLamouche, 2015), and it is based on the basis that sharing money is the principle in the financial system - especially when the spouses have not contracted over it. This idea is rejected in Islamic law for the following reasons:

First: It is contrary to the general principle, which is the right of man to own property, which shariah considers one of the requirements of instinct and one of the characteristics of freedom. Rather, it is one of the individual's human characteristics. This right is protected. It must be protected from any encroachment on it.

Second: Shariah considers marriage a reason for financial participation, and by this he established a contractual financial system that extends to the other party's Financial Disclosure, and even overrun him with all his money and one of them seized at the expense of the other's financial responsibility, and made marriage a reason for that, far from the high values and goals of him.

Third: Shariah makes the participation in all property, including what a person earns through his own effort and expense, and the principle is that the contribution is in the amount of the contribution and the percentage of the contribution, otherwise it is contrary to justice

Therefore, the law must be drafted so that the principle of the independent financial disclosure of both spouses is approved, and then the participation based on consent is made

the exclusion justified for joint liability, in addition to making it as much as the contribution is made.

This is what the Emirati legislator did. Article (62) of the Emirati law states the following: (An adult woman is free to dispose of her money, and the husband is not permitted to dispose of her money without her consent, for each of them has an independent financial responsibility, and if one of them participates with the other in developing money or building a home and the like. He has the right to revert to the other with his share in it upon divorce or death) (Dubai Judicial Institute, 2005).

It can also be formulated according to what was decided by the Council of the International Islamic Fiqh Academy, which is affiliated with the Organization of Islamic Cooperation. The latter decision states the following:

First: Each of the spouses has an independent financial responsibility, and according to that, each of them has the right to dispose of the money and rights he possesses, as compensation or as a donation.

Second: What each of the spouses owns due to or without the marriage contract is considered the private property of its owner, and it passes after him to his heirs.

Third: If the spouses agree with each other to share their money willingly and willingly, then there is no legal objection to that, and it is not permissible to impose that on them by binding appointment. (Organization of Islamic Cooperation, 2018).

In addition, the following could be added to it, "The spouses must agree to sharing their funds in an independent official document upon the conclusion of marriage or a subsequent contract".

Part 3: The reality of financial independence of the working wives in the Jordanian society

In this topic the empirical and part will be explained in detailed. This part presents a description for the study methodology, population, sample, and instruments. It also presents information about the instruments' validity and reliability. It presents information about the study's variables, procedures, and statistical methods. The latter methods were used to answer the study's questions.

The Study's Approach:

The descriptive approach was adopted to explore reality of the financial independence of working women in the Jordanian society from a legal and legal point of view, due to its relevance to the nature and objectives of the study.

The Study Sample:

The sample of the study consists of (500) women who work at the University of Jordan. (397) of the respondents are married. (103) of the respondents are not married. in terms of experience the respondent s classified as follows: (127) of the respondents have an experience that ranges between (1-5) years. (118) of the respondents have an experience that ranges between (6-10) years old. (114) of the respondents have an experience that ranges

between (11-15) years old. (141) of the respondents have an experience that exceed (15 years old).

The Study Instrument:

A measure for the financial disclosure independence

For exploring the reality of the independence of financial independence of working women in the Jordanian society, an independent measure for financial independence was developed. It was developed after reviewing previous literature, sources, references, and research. The initial form of the scale consists of (14) paragraphs. It sheds a light on three dimensions. The five-point Likert scale was adopted which consists of the following rating categories: (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree).

Validity and reliability of scale:

Virtual validity:

The initial version of the scale was passed to 12 experts. Those experts have much experience in the field of the Islamic law and legal judiciary. They were asked to assess the scale in terms of clarity, language, and relevance. They were asked to make modifications, addition, and deletions.

Some changes were made. The researchers kept the items that are approved by 80% of the experts or more. Thus, the final version of the scale consists of 14 items. The latter scale sheds a light on three dimensions:

1. The legal shariah dimension: Paragraphs No. (1-3).
2. The intellectual and social dimension: Paragraphs No. (4-12).
3. The legal dimension: Paragraphs No. (13-14).

Authenticity of the measuring instrument:

The authenticity validity was measured through passing the forms of the scale to an exploratory sample consists of (30) women. Those women were not chosen from the actual sample. The Pearson correlation coefficient value between the paragraph, the dimension and the total score of the scale, where the values of the correlation of the paragraphs of the legal shariah dimension ranged from (0.58- 0.84) with its dimension and between (0.45 - 0.63) with the total score of the scale, and the values of the correlation coefficients for the paragraphs of the social intellectual dimension ranged (0.49 - 0.68) with its distance and between (0.35 - 0.59) with the total score of the scale, and the value of the correlation coefficients for the paragraphs of the legal dimension ranged (0.51) - 0.76) with its dimension and between (0.40 - 0.68) with the total score of the scale, and all these values were statistically significant at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), indicating that the scale has a degree of authenticity suitable for the purposes of the study.

Reliability of the scale:

To assess the reliability of the scale and its dimensions, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient values are calculated after passing the scale forms to the exploratory sample (30 women).

The internal consistency values of the scale are (0.80), and the internal consistency values of their dimensions ranged between (0.68 - 0.78), and the stability of the repetition of the scale was also verified by re-applying the scale to the previous pilot sample using the method of testing and re-testing ((Test- Retest, with a time difference of two weeks between the first and second applications. Then, the Pearson correlation coefficient values are calculated. The overall Pearson correlation coefficient value is (0.83). The Pearson correlation coefficient values range between (0.74 - 0.81).

Scale correction:

The financial independence measure involves (14) items distributed in three dimensions, to be answered according to a five-point scale that includes the following alternatives: (very much in agreement and given when the scale is corrected with (5) degrees, largely approved and given (4) degrees, and I agree with a medium degree and are given (3) grades, and a little degree approved and given (two marks), and I never agree and are given (one score); as all the paragraphs were of a positive direction, and to arrive at an objective judgment on the averages of the responses of the individuals of the study sample, the range was calculated by subtracting the minimum from the upper limit ($5 - 1 = 4$), then dividing it by (4) ($4 \div 3 = 1.33$), and then this value was added to the lowest value in the scale (1) to determine the upper limit for this category, and thus the length of the categories became Low (less than 2.34), Medium from (2.34-3.66), and High (more than 3.66).

The Study's procedures:

To meet the objectives of the study, the researchers followed the following procedures:

1. They determined the study's problem and questions.
2. They reviewed the relevant theoretical literature.
3. They prepared the study's instrument in its initial form.
4. They chose the study sample and the targeted group.
5. They developed the instrument. validity and consistency of the instruments were assessed through passing the instrument to an exploratory sample and experts.
6. The relevant statistical methods were used to measure the validity and reliability of the instruments.
7. Official approvals to apply the scale were obtained.
8. They passed the study's instrument to the members of the sample in an electronic manner.
9. They analyzed the collected data through statistical analysis.
10. They reached results and discussed them based on the results of the previous studies. Then, recommendations were suggested.

The Study variables:

Study variables are classified into independent (predictors) variables, and dependent variables as follows:

Independent (predictors) variables:

1. Marital status (married or unmarried).
2. Years of service, and it is categorized as follows: (1-5) years, (6- 10) years, (11-15) years, and (more than 15 years).

Meanwhile, the **Dependent variable**, is the reality of financial independence of working wives.

Statistical analysis:

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze data. Means and standard deviations are calculated to answer the first question. The binary variance analysis (2-way ANOVA) was carried out to explore the effect of the two variables of the study. On the overall significance of the scale in its overall form, and the use of multiple double-way analysis of variance (2-way MANOVA) to answer the second question of the present study.

Study Results

1. The results that is related to the first study question, which is “What is the reality of the financial independence of working women in the Jordanian society?”

To answer this question, means and standard deviations of the respondent were calculated. The dimensions in **Table 1.** are arranged in a descending order based on the means as shown below.

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviations for dimensions of financial independence of the working wives.

No.	Rank	Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation	Level
2	1	Intellectual and social perspectives	3.85	0.66	High
3	2	Legal perspective	3.52	0.79	Moderate
1	3	Shariah-based perspective	3.07	0.89	Moderate
		Overall	3.48	0.54	Moderate

clear from **Table 1.** that the independence of financial independence of working women is moderate. The independence of financial disclosure of working women from intellectual and social perspective are high and ranked first. The independence of financial disclosure of working women from a legal perspective is moderate and ranked second. Meanwhile, the independence of financial disclosure of working women from Shariah-based perspective is moderate and ranked third.

Tables from **Table 2.** to **Table 4.** Shows the detailed results related to each area are. Those tables present means and standard deviations.

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviations for items related to financial independence of the

working women from social and intellectual perspectives.

No.	Paragraph	Mean	Standard Deviations	Level
1	The members of society consider the working wife as an additional source of income for the husband's income	4.34	0.88	High
2	Society places additional financial obligations on the working wife	4.22	0.93	High
3	Economic conditions oblige me to spend money on my family	4.12	1.00	High
4	My father has rights over my funds.	3.87	1.20	High
5	The society supports the idea of granting the husband the right to have shared ownership with the wife for the wife's funds. It supports the idea of granting the husband the right of disposal over the wife's funds.	3.86	1.20	High
6	The man believes that he has the right to own and dispose his wife's funds	3.78	1.32	High
7	There is a prevalent culture in society that considers it's taboo to have the wife owning all or part of the property that the family is residing at.	3.70	1.26	High
8	My children have rights over my funds	3.60	1.32	Moderate
9	Based on customs, I must spend money on my family	3.20	1.31	Moderate
Social intellectual perspective (as a whole)		3.85	0.66	High

Based on **Table 2.**, the reality of the independence of financial disclosure of working women from intellectual and social perspective is high. That is because the overall mean is 3.85. The means in the latter table are either high or moderate. The means in **Table 2.** are within the range of 4.34 – 3.20, since the mean of statement No. 1 is 4.34, and the mean of the statement labeled with No. 9 is 3.20 (i.e., Based on customs, I must spend money on my family).

The results in this regard may be attributed to changes in the world between the past and the present in materialistic aspects. They may be attributed to changes to the economic pattern of countries. Such changes changed the things considered luxury and the things considered necessities. That forms a pressure on the families, especially the families that are supported financially by one salary. Hence, many men seek searching for working women when intending to get married. They do that to have someone supporting them in handling the financial burdens. Therefore, there is a prevalent perception in society for the income of the working wife as an additional source of income for the husband. Having two sources of income in the family led to the rise of financial problematic issues.

The researchers found that the man believes that he has right over the wife's funds. They found that the husband believes that he has the right to dispose the wife's funds. They

found that there is a prevalent culture in society that considers it a taboo to have the wife owning all or part of the property that the family is residing at.

Through analyzing the contemporary reality in societies, one can find several proofs indicating that there are violations for women's rights. As for men, they enjoy more privileges than women in the contemporary societies. That may be attributed to the nature of customs and traditions. The latter nature is a patriarchal nature. Male children are taught - under such customs and traditions - to defend their beliefs even if they are false and wrong.

The latter results may be attributed to women's vulnerability. For instance, women may be beaten and deprived from their financial rights without defending themselves due to the prevalent customs. Therefore, some men believe that they have rights over their women's funds and the right to dispose such funds. Some men believe that they have the right to register what they want from women's assets in their names and dispose their women's funds in any manner they want.

The researchers of the present study found that the sampled women believe their fathers have rights over their funds. The respondents show moderate attitudes towards their children's rights over their funds. The latter result may be attributed to the fact that women want to show appreciation for efforts exerted by their parents for raising them up and providing them with education. The education provided by parents to women enabled them to work and get money. The latter result may be attributed to the fact that the sampled women believe that their husbands are responsible for supporting their children financially rather than them.

Table 3. The Means and Standard Deviations of the financial independence of the working wives from a legal perspective

No.	Paragraph	Mean	Standard Deviations	Level
1	The scholars specialized in law have been showing failure in explaining the laws related to the wives' funds	3.53	.92	Moderate
2	The legislator didn't regulate the issues related to the funds of the working wives	3.51	0.93	Moderate
Legal perspective (as a whole)		3.52	.79	Moderate

Based on **Table 3.**, the degree to which the working women have financial independence from a legal perspective is moderate. That is because the overall mean is 3.52. The means are within the range of 3.52 – 3.53.

The means of statement (1) which states “The scholars specialized in law have been showing failure in explaining the laws related to the wives' funds” is 3.53, meanwhile, The means of statement (2) is 3.51. The latter statement states the following: “The legislator didn't regulate the issues related to the funds of the working wives”.

Perhaps the matter in this is due to the fact that in the past the family was dominated by the presence of one breadwinner for it, which is the husband, but nowadays the wife has become working and sharing the burdens of life and living expenses with the husband, and she no longer stands silent in front of the digestion of her rights and has become demanding. The law recognizes her financial rights, but the marital relationship constitutes a moral barrier that prevents her from claiming her rights, which calls for the existence of new legislation controlling the issue of her participation in family spending, which is absent from the provisions of the law.

Table 4. The Means and Standard Deviations of the financial independence of the working wives from Shariah-based perspective

No.	Paragraph	Mean	Standard Deviations	Level
1	Women do not have knowledge about the rules of Shariah in terms of their rights to own and dispose their funds	3.21	1.33	Moderate
2	Sharia scholars have been showing failure in explaining the Sharia-based rules that are related to the wives' funds	3.46	1.25	Moderate
3	Women are obliged under the law to make contributions in supporting the family financially	2.54	1.41	Moderate
Shariah-based perspective (as a whole)		3.07	.89	Moderate

Based on **Table 4.**, the extent of having independent financial disclosure by the working women from a Shariah-based perspective is moderate. That is because the overall mean is 3.07. The means of all questions ranged between(2.54 - 3.46).

The means of statement (1) is (3.21). The latter statement states the following: (Women do not have knowledge about the rules of Shariah in terms of their rights to own and dispose their funds). The means of statement (3) is (2.54). The latter statement states the following: (Women are obliged under the law to make contributions in supporting the family financially)

Based on the results of the questionnaire, women don't have knowledge about the Sharia-based rules that are related to the wives' funds. The latter results may be attributed to the fact that courses at schools and universities don't promote knowledge about such rules.

In this regard, the failure of the scholars specialized in Shariah in explaining the Sharia-based rules related to women's funds. Therefore, there is a need for providing students in schools and universities with courses promoting knowledge about such rules. Such courses must promote knowledge about the rights and duties of husbands and wives. Due to the aforementioned failure of the scholars specialized in Shariah, there is a need to activate the role of the civil society institutions in promoting knowledge about Sharia-based rules related to women's funds.

Media plays a significant role in promoting knowledge about Sharia-based rules related to women's funds. That is because media is accessible by people of all socio-economic conditions. Media contributes to correcting the misconceptions that people have. It contributes to developing people's visions and perceptions in a manner that develops the society.

Results related to the second question:

Q.2.: (Is there any statistically significant difference - at the statistical significance level of ($\alpha = 0.05$)- between the respondents' attitudes towards the independence of financial independence of the working wives

in the reality of the independence of the financial responsibility of working women in the Jordanian society attributable to the marital status and number of years of service?)

To answer this question, arithmetic means, and standard deviations are calculated to explore respondent's attitudes in accordance with (marital status and number of years of service). The results are listed as shown in **Table 5** below.

Table 5.: The Means and Standard Deviations of the financial independence (as a whole) for individuals of the study sample according to the study variables (marital status, number of years of service)

No.	Variable	Category	Financial Independence (as a whole)	
			Mean	Standard Deviations
1	Social Status	Married	3.61	0.52
		Unmarried	3.65	0.60
2	No. of years of service	1 – 5 years	3.62	0.56
		6 – 10 years	3.64	0.44
		11 – 15 years	3.68	0.49
		Over 15 years	3.63	0.60

Based on **Table 5.**, it appears that there are differences between the respondent's independence level of financial independence, which can be attributed to (marital status, and the number of the years of experience). To identify whether those difference are significant, the analysis of binary variance (2-way ANOVA) was conducted (without interaction). The results of the latter analysis are shown in **Table 6.** below.

Table 6.The results of the analysis of binary variance 2-way ANOVA (without interaction) for the independence of financial independence (as a whole).

The Source of the Contrast	Sum Squares	Degrees Freedom	Average Total Squares	F-Value	Significance Statistic
Social status	0.484	1	0.484	1.655	0.199
Number of years of service	0.337	3	0.112	0.384	0.764

S t	The error	144.750	495	0.292		
	Total	145.691	499			

atistically significant at ($\alpha = 0.05$) level

Based on **Table 6.** above, there is not any statistically significant difference at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the respondent's independence level of financial disclosure which can be attributed to marital status. As well, there is not any statistically significant difference -at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$)- between the respondent's independence level of financial disclosure which can be attributed to the number of years of experience.

The researchers calculated means and standard deviations for the respondent's independence level of financial disclosure in accordance with (marital status, and the number of the years of experience). They results are as shown in **Table 7.**, below:

Table 7.: The arithmetic means and standard deviations for the respondent's independence level of financial independence in accordance with (marital status, and the number of the years of experience).

Variable	Level of Variables	Statistically significant	Dimensions of financial independence		
			Shariah	Social Intellectual	Legal
Social Status	married	Mean	3.04	3.89	3.49
		Standard Deviation	0.86	0.64	0.79
	Unmarried	Mean	3.18	3.69	3.59
		Standard Deviation	0.94	0.72	0.78
Number of years of service	1- 5 years	Mean	3.09	3.81	3.44
		Standard Deviation	0.94	0.66	0.80
	6-10 years	Mean	3.07	3.81	3.51
		Standard Deviation	0.87	0.58	0.78
	11-15 years	Mean	3.06	3.93	3.46
		Standard Deviation	0.78	0.64	0.76
	Over 15 years	Mean	3.05	3.83	3.62
		Standard Deviation	0.92	0.73	0.80

It is noticed from **Table 7.** above that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic circles of the dimensions of the independence of financial independence of the individuals respondent's when the levels of the two variables of the study (marital status, and the number of years of service) differ, with the aim of verifying the materiality of the apparent differences. Multiple bilateral variance analysis (MANOVA) (without interaction) was conducted, the results are stated in **Table 8.** below.

Table 8.: The result of multiple bilateral variance analysis (without interaction) for the dimension of financial independence in accordance with the study variables (marital status, and the number of the years of service).

Source of Variation	Dependent Variable	Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom	Average Sum of Squares	F-Value	Statistical significance
Social status Hotelling's trace=.031 Sig=0.002	The legal dimension	1.620	1	1.620	2.080	0.150
	The intellectual and social dimension	2.836	1	2.836	6.572	*0.011
	The legal dimension	1.470	1	1.470	2.396	0.122
Number of years of service Wilks' Lambda=.985 Sig=0.593	The legal dimension	0.001	3	0.000	0.001	0.973
	The intellectual and social dimension	0.905	3	0.302	0.699	0.553
	The legal dimension	3.212	3	1.071	1.746	0.157
Error	Legal dimension	385.472	495	0.779		
	The intellectual and social dimension	213.592	495	0.431		
	Legal dimension	303.639	495	0.613		
Total	Legal dimension	387.203	499			
	The intellectual and social dimension	217.580	499			
	Legal dimension	307.666	499			

Statistically significant at ($\alpha = 0.05$) level

It is evident from **Table 8.**, that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean of the dimension (intellectual and social) due to the variable of marital status among the study respondent's in favor of married women, as shown in **Table 7.**, and the absence of significant differences Statistically at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the means of the two dimensions (legal and sharia legal) due to the variable of marital status, as evidenced by **Table 8.**, there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the arithmetic

means for all dimensions of the independent responsibility finance for sample individuals to study in the variable number of years of service.

Conclusion

After studying and analyzing financial independence of the working wife, the following results were reached by the researchers:

First: Under Shariah, the working wife has a financial independence, the working wife have the rights to dispose part of her funds or all of it in any manner she wants. That applies provided that the latter manner is halal. Under Shariah, the working wife can conclude financial contracts by herself without assigning an intermediary.

Second: The husband does not have the rights over his wife's funds. He does not have the right to dispose his wife's funds without taking her permission. The provisions of Shariah aims at preserving the marital life and its stability and avoiding marital conflicts.

Third: It is not legally permissible to stipulate that the wife work outside the home in exchange for giving part of her salary and earning or sharing in the expenses due on the husband. Because such conditions are contrary to the requirements of the contract.

Fourth: The wife is not legally obligated to participate in the expenses due from the husband in the beginning, and it is not permissible to oblige her to do so, and if her exit results in additional expenses related to her, then she bears those expenses, and if the husband's income does not meet the needs of the household, then the wife's contribution to the alimony is a matter of good cohabitation and cooperation For the good.

Fifth: If the wife contributes - in Islamic law - with some of her money or the gain of her work in owning a house, real estate, or a commercial project, then she has the right to participate in the ownership of that house or project in proportion to the money that she contributed.

Sixth: Each of the spouses in Jordanian law has a financial independence, (*i.e.*, that is independent of the other), and the marital relationship is not a reason for the absence or merging of financial disclosure of the working wife.

Seventh: Stipulating the financial independence of the working wife in the Jordanian law is not sufficient to protect her rights, and the marital relationship is a moral barrier that prevents her from claiming her rights, so legal articles must be legislated for the issue of the participation of the working wife in family spending after it has become a reality that affects family stability.

Eighth: The legislator must enact legislations that acknowledge the financial independence of husbands and wives in terms of properties.

There must be legislations that acknowledge the shared financial independence of husband and wife, provided that the consent of spouses is taken. Taking such a consent shall contribute to achieving justice. It shall prevent people from getting married in the aim of engaging in a financial contractual relationship. It shall prevent having people getting rich from exploiting his/her spouse. It shall ensure that people create marital relationship for meeting moral goals.

Ninth: Community institutions must have an active role in promoting awareness in society about the legal and legal financial rights of women, especially among the ones intended to get married and married people. That shall contribute to reducing marital disputes.

Tenth: Developing the religious sense that forbids assaulting the rights of the people, both less and more.

Recommendations:

At the end of this research, and based on the above results, Researchers recommend the following:

1. Amending the Jordanian Personal Status Law through adding an article that regulates financial relations between spouses.
2. Passing the result of this study to specialists in order for them to benefit from this study and find a practical solutions that contribute to addressing the disputes between spouses.

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